

DEBONDING AND FRACTURE MECHANISMS OF PARTICULATE FILLED POLYPROPYLENE

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SUMMARY: Regularities of plastic deformation and fracture of particulate-filled polypropylene are analyzed. Experimental data on elongation at break ϵ_b of PP, filled by particles of different fraction and size are presented. Debonding and plastic flow micromechanisms are studied. The effect of micromechanisms on composite macroscopic behavior is analyzed. Two concentration regions of different debonding and flow micromechanisms were found. At low filler fraction ($< 15 - 20$ vol. %) particles debond independently at the initial stages of drawing and a microhomogeneous flow mechanism takes place. In this region deformation occurs with necking. Above a critical filler content, debonding proceeds in a correlated way with the formation of craze-like deformation zones transverse to the stretching axes. Concentration of craze-like zones is determined by filler fraction, particle size and the level of interfacial interaction. Whether microhomogeneous or craze-like mechanisms occur essentially determines the regularities of further deformation and fracture: localized or macrohomogeneous flow, ductile or quasi-brittle fracture, the drop or the rise of ultimate strains with increase of particle diameters.

KEYWORDS: particulate filled polypropylene, particle size, mechanical properties, debonding, plastic flow, craze, fracture mechanism.

INTRODUCTION

It is well established both by measurements and theoretical approaches that a level of interfacial interaction plays an important role in particulate filled composites deformation [1-5]. It is shown, in particular, that weakening of adhesion causes a diminution of composite stiffness [1,2,4] and yield stress [1,3,5]. Yield strain drops sharply with filler fraction in a case of well-bonded particles and slightly diminishes in an opposite case [3,5].

A simplified model of composite fracture was proposed in [5] in framework of deformation theory of plasticity. It is based on the numerical analysis of stress-strain distribution (SSD) and critical value criterion of maximum shear strain. The model predicts a sharp drop of ultimate elongation with an increase in filler fraction in a case of a perfect interfacial bond and a gradual decrease of the last in a case of poor adhesion. The predictions are in qualitative agreement with experimental data, however the model does not account two important factors.

An effect of the particle size is the first one. Debonding in the particulate filled polymers leads to a formation of the pores on initial stages of deformation. Further growth and confluence of the pores seems to be an adequate mechanism of ductile materials (PP, PE)

rupture [6,7]. In a case of the brittle material a dramatic drop in the strength with an increase in a defect size forms a basic point of a linear fracture mechanics. Whenever pores are the defects responsible for the fracture of high plastic materials, their size likely affects on fracture parameters in analogous manner. From the other side not only absolute size, but also concentration of the defects should determine fracture parameters. This concentration in turn is determined by a level of interfacial interaction. As was shown in [8,9], the particle diameter, \bar{d} , is responsible for this level, namely, the debonding stress, σ_d , decreases with an increase in \bar{d} . In accordance with a model of [5], the less is a portion of debonded particles, the less should be ultimate strain.

A second simplification of a model [5] is in a consideration of uniform SSD. High plastic polymers and composite on their basis mostly deform in heterogeneous manner with formation and growth of the neck. In this case a sharp reduction in composite deformability (ductile-brittle transition) clearly should coincide with a disappearance of a strain hardening, i.e. equality between a strength σ_b and a neck stress σ_n [10].

In the present study an effect of particle content and size on macroscopic behavior of particulate-filled PP is analyzed. An establishment of the correlation between debonding processes at the initial stage of deformation, plastic flow mechanisms and composite fracture regularities is the goal of this investigation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Isotactic PP was used as a matrix. Polymer molecular weight characteristics, measured by a GPC method, were: $\bar{M}_w=6.3 \times 10^5$, $\bar{M}_w/\bar{M}_n=3.5$. Aluminum hydroxide $Al(OH)_3$ was used as the filler. Four fractions of mean, \bar{d} , minimum, d_{min} , and maximum, d_{max} , diameters were used: 1 (0.5-1.5), 2.5 (1.5-5), 8 (4-16) and 25 (5-50) μm .

Composites were prepared in a "Brabender" mixing chamber at $T=190^\circ C$, duration of mixing was 10 min. Calcium stearate (2 wt.% of the filler fraction) was added to avoid filler aggregation. Polymer degradation was prevented by Topanol (0.3 wt.%) and dilauriltiodipropionate (0.5 wt.%). Filler content was in the range 0-70 wt.% (0-47 vol.%). A filler surface treatment by octamethylcyclotetrasiloxane was used into the series of high filler content to reduce adhesive interaction.

The specimens for mechanical testing were prepared by the molding at $T=190^\circ C$ and the pressure $p=10 MPa$ with subsequent cooling under the pressure. The drawing of the blade shaped samples was performed on the "Instron-1122" at the room temperature and strain rate $0.67 min^{-1}$.

The structure of the deformed composite samples was observed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) with the use of "JSM-35C".

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The effect of filler fraction and size on ultimate elongations of particulate-filled PP.

The dependencies of the elongations at break ϵ_b on the filler volume fraction and particle size are shown in Fig. 1. A series of regularities is seen from these data.

1. Ultimate strains decrease with the rise of filler content. The increase of ϵ_b in the case of large particles ($\bar{d} = 25 \mu m$) in the range of filler fraction $15\% \leq \Phi \leq 30 \text{ vol.}\%$ is an interesting exclusion from this regularity. It will be discussed below. Here we note that only two publications (Fu, Wang and Shen [11,12]) are known to us as other experimental evidence on the rise of polyolefines fracture properties with an increase of rigid filler content. Authors found brittle-ductile impact strength transition for the HDPE- $CaCO_3$ composites in the case of filler surface modification by phosphate.
2. The ductile-brittle transition is rather sharp in the case of small particles ($\bar{d} = 1,2,5 \mu m$) and occurs at $\Phi_{br} \approx 25 \text{ vol.}\%$. The increase of \bar{d} leads to the more smooth concentration dependencies and to the shift to the right of Φ_{br} ($\Phi_{br} \approx 36 \text{ vol.}\%$ for $\bar{d} = 8 \mu m$).
3. An increase of the particle size leads to the drop of the elongation at break at small filler fraction ($< 15 \text{ vol.}\%$) and to the rise of the ϵ_b above $\Phi \approx 30 \text{ vol.}\%$. Intermediate region is characterized by the extreme-type size dependencies (Fig. 2).

Three regions of volume fraction are also characterized by different modes of macroscopic deformation.

Fig.1. The elongation at break versus filler volume fraction for different particle size

Below $\Phi = 15 \text{ vol.}\%$ the drawing is accompanied by formation and propagation of a neck. Strain-hardening is briefly recognized in the case of small particles. This circumstance

provides propagation of the neck all through the sample. However, the increase of the particle size causes the drop in strain-hardening. It results in the fracture of samples, filled by 14 vol.% of large inclusions ($\bar{d} = 25 \mu m$), at the initial or intermediate stage of the neck propagation.

In the intermediate region ($15 \text{ vol.}\% \leq \Phi \leq 30 \text{ vol.}\%$) a tendency to unstable neck propagation is observed. Formation of two or three necks is seen in the case of small particles. The increase of \bar{d} leads to the disappearance of the neck and the tendency to homogeneous flow.

Above 30 vol.%, filled by small particles ($\bar{d} = 1,2,5 \mu m$) composites break in quasi-brittle manner with formation of a narrow neck. The increase of \bar{d} provides macrohomogeneous flow, but up to the certain threshold, dependent of particle size. For the composites of $\bar{d} = 8 \mu m$ a tendency to the formation of a narrow neck and quasi-brittle fracture is revealed at $\Phi \cong 36 \text{ vol.}\%$.

The surface treatment of small particles by octamethylcyclotetrasiloxane rises elongation at break of composites filled by 28 vol.% and 36 vol.% (Fig. 2, dashed lines) [13]. This procedure causes the transition from localized flow and quasi-brittle failure to macrohomogeneous deformation and ductile fracture in the case of $\bar{d} = 2,5 \mu m$.

Experimental data on filler fraction and size dependencies of ultimate strains and microscopical observations of samples deformed demonstrate the change of debonding and flow micromechanisms at Φ_{cz} between 15 and 20 vol.%.

Fig.2. The elongations at break versus particle diameter. Dashed lines point to surface treatment.

The transition of debonding and plastic flow micromechanisms with the increase of filler fraction.

Exfoliation along the surface of a single inclusion obviously results in the change of SSD in its close vicinity. So, it is natural to expect the occurrence of different debonding micromechanisms depending on particle content.

Uncorrelated debonding and microhomogeneous flow mechanism.

The change of SSD is not noticeable far from the source of this change. So, in the case of the large interparticle distance, or, equivalently, at a small filler fraction debondings of different particles should proceed independently. Uncorrelated debonding mechanism (Fig.3a) causes microhomogeneous flow (see Fig.3b, which corresponds to the region of the developed neck). A picture of this type was observed by SEM for the composite samples with $\Phi < 15$ vol.% [14]. We underline the following features.

1. Exfoliation occurs along the surfaces of all the particles.
2. Longitudinal elongation of the every pore formed is equal, with a good precision, to the draw ratio mean elongation of the neck region (microhomogeneous deformation).

Fig.3: Scheme representation of uncorrelated (a), correlated (c) debonding micromechanisms and sequent microhomogeneous (b), and craze-like (d) plastic flow

Correlated debonding and craze-like flow micromechanism.

Quite another situation takes place in the case $\Phi > 15-20$ vol.%. Debonding of the single inclusion considerably changes SSD of a neighbor because of the small interparticle distance. The maximum stress intensity in the uniaxially stretched composites is reached in the area of

a pore equator. It should result in correlated debondings of neighbor particles and the formation of the craze-like microporous zones, extended in the direction transverse to the stretching axes. Correlated debonding (Fig.3c) causes the craze-like flow mechanism (Fig.3d). Such picture was observed by SEM for the composite samples with $\Phi > 20$ vol.% [14]. Contrary to the previous case, debonding is characterized by the following features. A noticeable portion of the particles outside the craze-like zones remain bonded.

Because of the sharp difference in the compliances, further deformation mainly concentrates inside the craze-like microporous zones, whenever the other regions remain weakly stretched. The first regularity may be clarified by the following estimation of the screen effect efficiency, which is in the drop of the stress in the area of craze banks, caused by formation of micropores inside. Let us denote the debonding stress (the stress value sufficient for the exfoliation along the surface of the given particle) by σ_d and the stress of polymer bulkhead inside the crack by σ^{bh} . It is natural to suggest that the pore fraction inside the craze-like zones is equal to the filler volume content Φ and to use the minimum cross section area estimation for the calculation of the stress, σ^{cz} , tightening the craze-like zone banks:

$$\sigma^{cz} = \sigma^{bh} (1 - \alpha \Phi^{2/3}). \quad (1)$$

Correlation between σ_d and σ^{cz}

$$\sigma^{cz} \geq \sigma_d \quad (2)$$

determines the conditions for the further debonding of the particles in the vicinities of the craze banks. It is seen that even in the case of the weak adhesive strength (low σ_d value, which is analyzed in the present paper) new debondings formation in the process of further stretching will be forbidden at sufficiently high filler content.

As noted, the increase of the particle size results in a drop of the debonding stress σ_d [8,9] and thereby in the rise of pore concentration. The surface treatment by the antiadhesive component is another route for a debonding stress decrease [9,13].

The stage of secondary debondings depends upon the state of bulkheads in the primary crazes. σ^{bh} and, hence, σ^{cz} can be raised in the process of further drawing, if the bulkheads deform in the elastic or strain hardening region. σ^{bh} is a fixed value, equal to the polymer matrix yield stress σ_Y , if the bulkheads are in the stage of plastic flow. So, if the craze-like flow mechanism is realized, debonding may occur, not only at the beginning of drawing, but at the developed or even final stages. In the case of the sample, filled by 36 vol.% of small ($\bar{d} = 2.5 \mu m$) particles only few zones are seen outside the narrow neck. Inside the neck their concentration is much higher because of the strain-hardening stage of the bulkheads in deformation zones.

Macroscopic consequences of microhomogeneous or craze-like flow.

Localized or macrohomogeneous flow.

Unfilled PP is characterized by a well-emphasized extreme-type engineering diagram and localized plastic flow, but the true stress increases with draw ratio. An extreme type of the engineering diagram is caused by a conservation of volume and, therefore, a drop of the cross-section area on draw.

The increase of pore concentration in the filled PP leads to a more noticeable growth of

material volume on deformation and, hence, to a less drop of the cross-section area. In the framework of a microhomogeneous mechanism ($\Phi \leq 15$ vol.%), debonding occurs for every particle at the initial stage of deformation. However, because of the small filler fraction, the volume of the pores formed is not sufficient for the qualitative change of engineering diagrams and the samples deform with necking for the every particle size studied.

The transition to macrohomogeneous flow would take place at the further increase of filler fraction if the microhomogeneous mechanism remains valid. But the change of microhomogeneous flow mechanism by the craze-like process complicates the situation. If σ_d is low, debonding in accordance with (1), (2) is not forbidden and the volume of the pores formed becomes sufficient for the change of the engineering diagram from the extreme to increasing ones. This is the reason for macrohomogeneous deformation of high filled composites ($\Phi > 20$ vol.%) in the cases of large ($\bar{d} = 8,25 \mu m$) inclusions or small ones ($\bar{d} = 2,5 \mu m$), treated by anti-adhesive component. In the case of untreated small particles the criterion (2) of debonding is not valid, because of the increase of the debonding stress. So, micropore concentration remains low and the samples deform with the necking.

Ductile and quasi-brittle fracture.

The fracture properties of particulate-filled ductile polymers are determined by the growth and confluence of micropores, formed in the process of debonding. So, debonding and the consequent flow mechanism are extremely important.

In the framework of microhomogeneous flow mechanism ($\Phi < 15$ vol.%) a filler fraction can be sufficiently low for the complete adhesive failure at the initial stages of deformation (composite yield stress σ_Y decreases with Φ , but can remain higher than σ_d). The composites characterized by ductile fracture. The drop of ε_b with the increase of particle size (Fig. 1, the initial portions of the curves, Fig. 2, $\Phi = 15$ vol.%) is governed by the geometric factor of rupture, which is in the aggravation of fracture parameters with the growth of the size of a defect, responsible for fracture.

In the framework of the craze-like mechanism, complete debonding is not obtained because of the screen effect discussed. In this case the main part of deformation is concentrated in the narrow microporous zones, so ultimate strains depend upon the specific amount of the last by means of at least two reasons. The first is the increase of the elongation due to the increase in the concentration of the deformed regions. The second reason is the rise of the strain at break of polymer bulkheads inside the craze, as a result of the decrease of the local strain rate, at fixed value of the last, with an increase of the crazes density. Therefore, geometric factor of fracture contradicts with the debonding one, which is in the change of degree of debonding processes completion. The influence of this contradiction on ε_b is illustrated by the intermediate and final portions of the curves in Fig. 1 and by the plots of Fig.2, corresponded to $\Phi = 28$ and 36 vol.%.

Debonding stress distributions, ($dV_d/d\sigma d\sigma$ is a volume fraction of the particles, debonded in the stress interval between σ and $\sigma+d\sigma$), are schematically represented at Fig.4. The increase of filler fraction does not noticeably change the debonding stress [9], i.e., the abscissa position of the curves 1-3 in Fig. 4a, but gives a proportional increase of the ordinate. The porosity of the sample should increase due to this factor. However, the stress σ^{cz} in the vicinities of the

craze banks drops with Φ in accordance with correlation (1). Competition between these two factors admits the rise or drop of craze-like zones density and, therefore, the existence of increasing or decreasing portions of ultimate strains dependencies upon filler fraction. This phenomenon is the reason of the rise of ε_b with Φ in the region $15 \text{ vol.}\% \leq \Phi \leq 30 \text{ vol.}\%$ in the case $\bar{d} = 25 \mu\text{m}$ and the drop of the last in the case of small particles (Fig. 1). Dramatic diminution of the microporous zones density provides the transition from ductile to quasi-brittle fracture. The corresponding filler fraction, Φ_{br} , depends upon the debonding stress (which is the decreasing function of \bar{d}) and should be shifted to the higher Φ with the increase of particle size. This regularity is experimentally confirmed by the increase of Φ_{br} from $\cong 25 \text{ vol.}\%$ for $\bar{d} = 1$, and $2.5 \mu\text{m}$ to $\Phi_{br} \cong 36 \text{ vol.}\%$ for $\bar{d} = 8 \mu\text{m}$ (Fig. 1).

Fig.4: Scheme representation of the debonding stress distributions: (a) - for different filler fractions ($\Phi_1 < \Phi_2 < \Phi_3$) and fixed particle size; (b) - for the various particle diameters ($\bar{d}_1 > \bar{d}_2 > \bar{d}_3$) and fixed filler fraction. Vertical lines denote the stresses σ^{cz} in the vicinities of the craze banks (see formula (1))

Contrary, at the fixed filler fraction the σ^{cz} value remains unchanged, whenever the change of the particle size results in the horizontal shift of the debonding stress distribution (Fig4b). The surface treatment by the anti-adhesive component facilitates debonding [9] and is an alternative way to achieve such a shift. So, at the high filler content, debonding is most important and causes an increase of ε_b with the increase of inclusion size (Fig. 2, $\Phi = 36$ vol.%, solid line). Competition between adhesive and geometric factors of fracture (the last remains valid in framework of the craze-like mechanism) is the reason of the extreme size dependence of ε_b at $\Phi=28$ vol.% (Fig. 2, solid line) and at high filler content in the case of anti-adhesive coating of the particles (Fig. 2, $\Phi = 28$ and 36 vol.%, dashed lines).

CONCLUSIONS

1. Fracture properties of particulate-filled PP have been studied in the wide range of filler fraction and size.
2. Two debonding micromechanisms and the transition between them at $\Phi_{cz} \sim 15\%$ were discovered. The first is uncorrelated debonding at the initial stages of deformation and occurs at low Φ (< 15 vol.%). The second micromechanisms is correlated debonding of neighbor particles inside the narrow zones, transverse to the loading axis.
3. Two different material flow mechanism - microhomogeneous and the craze-like one ($\Phi > 15$ vol.%) - have been found. In the case of uncorrelated debonding the microhomogeneous deformations form in the neighborhood of the pores. The correlated debondings of neighbor particles results in the craze-like flow mechanism. In this case plastic deformation is mainly concentrated inside craze-like regions.
4. An increase of micropore fraction is the reason for the transition from localized drawing (with necking) to macrohomogeneous draw.
5. Two factors of composite failure are formulated: a geometric one, which is in the drop of fracture properties with an increase of particle (pore) size; and a debonding factor, which is in the formation of the sources of fracture in the processes of phase exfoliation and in the change of degree of debonding processes completion dependent of particle size.
6. In the framework of microhomogeneous flow mechanism, geometric factor governs the fracture, and ultimate elongations decrease with an increase of filler content and particle size.
7. In the framework of craze-like mechanism, the debonding factor of fracture plays an important role. The increase of debonding stress with the decrease of the particle size results in the drop of the craze-like zone concentration and in a decrease of Φ_{br} of the ductile-brittle transition. Competition between geometric and debonding factors causes extreme dependence of the elongation at break upon \bar{d} in the intermediate region $15 \text{ vol.}\% < \Phi < 30 \text{ vol.}\%$. At $\Phi > 30 \text{ vol.}\%$ ultimate strains increase with the rise of \bar{d} , due the increase of deformation zone concentration.

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